

POLITICAL IMAGE AND TECHNOLOGIES OF ITS FORMATION

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In the 21st century, humanity has entered a qualitatively new stage . Today, when the world is undergoing unprecedented changes, new ways of mastering the social space, including its technology, are becoming a broad picture. From this point of view, both social relations and political processes are becoming objects of technology. The main goal of using political technologies is to achieve effective performance of political subjects' tasks and obligations. It is well known that the growth of mass literacy, the development of the Internet, the meeting of the most modern requirements of smartphones, etc. as a result, citizens are demanding that the authorities fully fulfill their functions and not destroy them due to irresponsibility. In most cases, public scrutiny and pressure force political groups and interest groups to change their positions. If the use of socio-political advertising as a technology in influencing political processes allows to actively influence social life, the use of the technology of creating a politician's image serves to realize the talent and potential of political subjects.

Image plays an important role in politics. Subjects of image politics are an important form of political capital and at the same time a mechanism for its reproduction. Originally, the term "image" was used in trade advertising to differentiate one type of product. In the 60s of the 20th century, with the development of new methods of organizing election campaigns, this concept began to be widely used in the United States to distinguish political leaders. As a

result, the image changed from an economic category to a political category. In the economy, the image helps to sell products, in banking it attracts customers, and in politics it serves to form a positive attitude towards one or another politician.

The image is the essence of advertising creativity. After all, in the implementation of socio-political advertising, it is important to create the image or image of the candidate and reflect it in the advertisement. Because an image "materializes" only when it is made public, and an image that is not made public does not exist. The importance of the image increases in the candidate's victory in the elections, in ensuring the legitimacy of power in crisis situations, and in making the political leader popular. According to experts, "actions of image makers can provide an average of 15-20% of votes to a capable candidate" ¹.

In socio-political advertising, the subject-object relationship has its own characteristics. A candidate's communication with voters is often indirect. On the one hand, this is related to the need to influence a large number of people (using mass media for this), and on the other hand, it is related to the fact that a person cannot show his whole human nature and qualities in front of the public. Therefore, a certain image, which includes the real qualities of the candidate and the ideal qualities that reflect the interests of the electorate, is separated from him. The image acts as a mediator between the leader and the masses, inspires the people, and expresses the hopes and dreams of the people. The voter accepts exactly this impression, that is, the image. Qualities related to the leader's attitude to certain politics, worldview, biography and appearance are expressed as a whole in the image based on the wishes of the electorate.

In fact, considering that most voters do not have the opportunity to communicate directly with the leader, we understand that the choice depends

¹ Malishevsky N.N. Technology and organization selection. — Mn.: Harvest, 2003 , 46 - p.

more on his image than on the candidate. In this case, the image of the candidate is more important than who he is. In this regard, the organizers of R. Nixon's election campaign in 1968 explained the strategy of their actions in this way: "we need to change not the person, but the impression received about him" ².

The Latin term "image" means "in Uzbek language image, figure, symbol, beauty, famous, important, handsome, handsome, good-looking, prestigious, influential" ³. In the language of modern communication, the image is interpreted as a multifaceted phenomenon. From this point of view, there are a large number of definitions and classifications of the image.

Image means "a purposefully developed and promoted image of a candidate ⁴. " Uzbek scientist U. Karaboev writes: "The image is formed on the basis of the crystallized vision of the person around him. More precisely, the remarkable aspects, abilities, and activities of a person appear after being recognized by many people ⁵. If we connect socio-political advertising with the implementation process, the image is understood as "a visual representation of reality that embodies the idea of advertising in an effective, memorable and symbolic form. In this case, sound, visual and verbal signs reveal the suggestive functions of the advertising product ⁶.

"Creating an image in politics means the process of forming an image of a political subject that attracts people's attention in order to achieve a political goal ⁷. " In other words, the image is a set of perceptions formed by people about a political figure on the basis of received information. The image also embodies the

² G. G. Pocheptsov. Imageology. M.: Refl - book, K.: Wakler. — 2000, p . 546 .

³ Karaboev U. Image and imigeology // Society and management, 1999, issue 1-2 , page 46 .

⁴ Malishevsky N.N. Technology and organization selection. — Mn.: Harvest, 2003 , p. 42.

⁵ Karaboev U. Image and imigeology // Society and management, 1999, issue 1-2 , page 47 .

⁶ Uchenova V.V., Starykh N.V. Kak rodilas advertisement. — M., 1992, p . 5 .

⁷ Solovev A.I. Political science: Political theory, political technology: Uchebnik dlya studentov vuzov / A.I.Solovev. — M.: Aspect Press, 2006, p . 519 .

impression taken from the program documents, statements, decisions of the leader. When creating an image in politics, a treasure of various means and methods of targeted influence on the audience is used based on the interests of a particular person or group claiming public recognition.

Summarizing the definitions, the image is manifested as "a set of certain qualities that remind people of a certain person", "an image capable of giving a person unique qualities", "your perception by others", "the general image of your personality in the eyes of others". Based on research on the image, some of its characteristics and signs can be distinguished:

- an image represents a simplified portrait of its object. A distinctive feature of the dominant image is considered — this is a reduced message, a large volume of information about the object is transformed into a limited set of symbols in the image medium;
- the image emphasizes the uniqueness and uniqueness of the object, thus the image is fundamentally different from the stereotype that summarizes the events;
- the image is clear, but variable; it is constantly changing, adapted to the requirements of the existing situation, the wishes of the audience; the exposure of the recipient of the information is controlled;
- this is feedback communication. Messages are created taking into account the expected exposure of the public;
- the image corresponds to a certain extent to the object being advertised and at the same time idealizes it, exaggerating its useful, acceptable features or "enriching" the object with additional social, ideological, psychological values that meet the wishes and expectations of advertising consumers;
- although attached to the image of its object, the image operates according to its own laws;
- the image combines the characteristics of the object with the imagination of the audience;

□ the image occupies an intermediate position between reality and desire, between perception and imagination ⁸.

The image performs a number of social tasks: a) identification, thanks to this task, the candidate's image becomes easily recognizable; b) idealization, due to this task, the created image of the candidate is far from his real qualities; c) comparison, this task allows to distinguish from other images ⁹. In addition, communicative, nominative, aesthetic and address functions of the image are distinguished in scientific sources ¹⁰. The communicative task, first of all, assumes that the image serves to facilitate the audience's perception of information about politics. In addition, as a result of conveying to the audience the qualities of the candidate that are favorable to the electorate, creating a comfortable and acceptable environment for his acceptance by people also represents the communicative function of the image. As a special type of communication, the image acts as a special "mirror" for its hero.

The nominative function of the image means that it helps distinguish the candidate from other people, demonstrates his unique qualities, and draws attention to his advantages. His appearance, attractiveness, and the way he dresses play an important role in creating the leader's image. This is where the aesthetic function of the image is revealed. The function of address implies that there is a connection between the image and its target audience.

At this point, it is appropriate to cite image classifications from a number of sources. From the point of view of political communications, it is important to distinguish between objective, subjective, ideal and modelable image. An

⁸ Greenberg T.N. Political technology: PR and advertising: Ucheb. Posobie dlya studentov vuzov / T.E. Grinberg. — M.: Aspekt Press, 2005, pp. **160-161** .

⁹ Politiko -administrativnoe upravlenie: Uchebnik / Pod obshch.ed. V.S. Komarovskiy, L.V. Smorgunova. - M.: Izd-vo RAGS, 2004, p. 447.

¹⁰ Greenberg T.N. Political technology: PR and advertising: Ucheb. Posobie dlya studentov vuzov / T.E. Grinberg. — M.: Aspect Press, 2005, p . **161** .

objective or true image means "impression formed by voters about a certain candidate" ¹¹. The objective image does not have a permanent character, but changes when the political situation changes, as well as as a result of the efforts of the creators of the political campaign strategy. "The candidate and his team's perception of how the voters see the candidate" ¹² is an example of subjective image.

The ideal image is "a set of qualities of a hypothetical candidate that best meet a specific pre-election situation" ¹³. " These are perceptions of electoral groups about desirable leadership qualities. However, it must be admitted that man is not perfect. Therefore, it is natural that attempts to determine the ideal image of a candidate arouse distrust in people. So, in the implementation of socio-political advertising, it is necessary to create an image close to reality, relying on the objective qualities of the candidate. Solving this task requires creating a modelable image. "The modelable (strategic) image is the image that the candidate team and involved specialists are trying to create" ¹⁴. " It is the image that is being modeled that is transmitted to the audience. Strengthening of the modeled image in the minds of voters ensures the effectiveness of socio-political advertising. Because the transformation of the image to be modeled into an objective image, that is, an image that is strengthened in the minds of voters, is the most optimal case for advertising strategy.

According to one of the experts in the field of socio-political advertising, D. Whittner, "a candidate must have one or more qualities that inspire us, he must be

¹¹ Ilyasov F.N. "Political marketing." Art and science are pobejdat na vyborax". M.: Izdatelstvo IMA - press, 2000, p . 52 .

¹² Greenberg T.N. Political technology: PR and advertising: Ucheb. Posobie dlya studentov vuzov / T.E. Grinberg. — M.: Aspect Press, 2005, p . 162 .

¹³ Malishevsky N.N. Technology and organization selection. — Mn.: Harvest, 2003 , p. 43.

¹⁴ Ilyasov F.N. "Political marketing." Art and science are pobejdat na vyborax". M.: Izdatelstvo IMA - press, 2000, p. 5-3 .

active, passionate, appear to be a winner, be sympathetic, sincere, self-confident and "Persistence should shine ¹⁵." In addition, the leader should be perceived as a person who knows how to succeed and win. In creating the leader's image, it is also appropriate to show his readiness to take responsibility for the affairs of the country, government, and region.

In order for the candidate to match the image of a true leader, it is important to cover not only his present, but also his past accordingly. Therefore, the genre of biography occupies a special place in socio-political advertising. Biographical information used in socio-political advertising is sorted in terms of whether it matches the ideals of the audience. Unwanted information in the leader's biography is excluded, "forgotten" or interpreted as necessary.

When creating an image of a candidate, it is necessary to consider not only their positive qualities, but also their negative characteristics. The presence of some less significant negative qualities in the image of the candidate does not weaken the image, but rather enriches it. This brings the politician's image closer to the public, enriches it with purely human qualities, and in exchange for this, the candidate gains "credibility".

In the image, the image of the future offered by the candidate is important. Therefore, in order to win elections, it is necessary to focus on developing a thorough program or editing an existing program to suit the interests of interest groups. Socio-political advertising, of course, simplifies this task, because it turns the conflict between political programs into a conflict between alternative ideas. However, precisely because of this, socio-political advertising becomes an effective tool of beneficial action.

When analyzing socio-political advertising as a means of forming the image of political subjects, it is necessary to focus on other subjects of politics.

¹⁵ Lisovsky S.F. Political advertising. Chapter 1 . <http://evartist.people.ru/text/7/03.htm#ftn11>

After all, socio-political advertising covers the advertising of political parties (associations), state administration bodies and public organizations, in addition to individual citizens participating in political activities. The image of parties is also created by means of socio-political advertising, and its promotion serves to attract supporters, attract new members to its ranks, convey the ideas and principles of the new party to the general public, or encourage members of society to participate in a specific political event.

One of the widely used techniques for image formation is related to giving the opinion of a famous person about this candidate. In this case, the psychological law of copying the qualities of a famous person begins to apply, more precisely, the qualities of a famous person are transferred to the subject of advertising, thereby instilling trust in him. Such support allows the candidate to speak in the third person, which means that the person supporting the candidate can say things that the candidate is uncomfortable talking about himself.

To sum up, the effective performance of tasks such as increasing the authority of a political subject, creating its attractive image in the public mind, expanding the number of its supporters, influencing political opponents, forming the electoral inclinations of the population, and mobilizing the public to support a certain political force, make political technologies widely used in political processes. requires application. In order to increase the effectiveness of advertising of a political subject, it is necessary to work seriously on creating its image, and to use technologies that serve to create the leader's image wisely. From this point of view, the special and scientific analysis of the issue of creating the image of political subjects by means of socio-political advertising serves to study the problem raised in the article.